

MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING OF TIME DEPENDENT FAILURE IN TRANSVERSELY LOADED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The time dependent fracture behaviour of transversely loaded E-glass/epoxy composites is investigated using a micromechanical approach in combination with a three-dimensional elasto-viscoplastic stress-strain relation, which is able to describe the time dependent behaviour of the epoxy matrix. Numerical simulations show that such an approach in combination with a matrix failure criterion based on a maximum shear strain provides a good description for the rate dependent transverse strength of unidirectional composites. Furthermore, such a strain criterion is also able to describe creep lifetime of transversely loaded composites.

INTRODUCTION

Models for the prediction of strength of composite materials are generally directed to short-term failure using laminate analysis based on classical mechanics, coupled with a common failure theory such as maximum stress or maximum strain concepts [1]. Since almost all engineering components are subjected to load and environmental histories which differ strongly over the service time of the component, it is clear that there is a need for the development of new approaches for the prediction of failure of composites which enable us to include time-variable circumstances. In case of matrix dominated failure it seems therefore obvious to investigate the time and stress dependent failure of the polymer matrix. Failure of polymers is in most cases preceded by yielding. For brittle polymers, yielding leads almost instantaneously to fracture, whereas for ductile polymers, yielding initiates the formation of a neck, which stabilization and propagation is the result of strain hardening [2]. In polymer physics, relatively straightforward analyses have been developed which have proven their applicability to yielding of glassy polymers in multiaxial stress fields [3-5]. Previous studies recognised already the importance of a multiaxial stress state in the matrix for the initiation of transverse composite failure [6-8]. In order to describe yielding of the matrix under a multiaxial stress situation as encountered in composite materials, the yield behaviour of an epoxy system, which has been used as the matrix system for the glass fibre-reinforced composites in this study, was characterized under various multiaxial loading conditions. With recent developments in three-dimensional constitutive modelling of large strain plasticity in amorphous polymers [9], the numerical simulation of the behaviour of the

polymer matrix under complex loading conditions is well within reach. In previous work a constitutive model, which describes yield in multi-axial stress and strain fields similar to the approach of Ward and Duckett [3,4], was implemented into a finite element code [10]. In this research this technique was employed, in combination with micromechanics, to evaluate short-term and long-term transverse failure of unidirectional glass/epoxy laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

A rather brittle epoxy system of Ciba Geigy (Araldite LY556/HY 917/DY070) was used as matrix system in this study. This epoxy system is based on bisphenol A with an anhydride curing agent. E-glass fibres (Silenka 0.84-M28) were used as reinforcement material. For the characterization of the neat epoxy, plates were manufactured by casting the epoxy resin into a heated mould and curing them for 4h at 80°C and 8h at 140°C. From these epoxy plates, samples were cut and milled into the various test specimens. Unidirectional composites were manufactured by filament winding, where fibre strands were impregnated in a heated epoxy bath and wound uniformly on a framework. The impregnated fibres were subsequently placed in a mould and cured in a hot-press. The resulting composite plates had a thickness of 1.25 mm and a fibre volume fraction of approximately 50%. From these unidirectional laminates transverse three-point bending specimens were cut with a length of 50 mm and a width of 25 mm. The edges of all samples, both reinforced and unreinforced, were carefully polished.

Testing

In order to characterize the yielding behaviour of the matrix material under complex stress and strain fields various tests are needed. In this research five different (multi-axial) tests, viz. uniaxial extension, uniaxial compression, planar extension, planar compression and simple shear, were performed on the pure matrix material at strain rates varying over several decades. Uniaxial tensile tests were performed at different strain rates and were in accordance with ASTM D638-91. Uniaxial compression samples were end-loaded and measured 25x6x6 mm. Planar extension test samples had a thickness in the testing region of 2 mm over a length of 10 mm and a width of 50 mm. Planar compression tests were performed on dog-bone shaped specimens measuring 85x20x4 mm. In the test-section the specimens were supported by steel plates to create a plane strain condition. Simple shear tests, according to ASTM D4255-83, were performed on samples with a thickness of 2 mm and a length of 100 mm. The distance between the grips was 10 mm, resulting in an aspect ratio of 10. Unidirectional composites were tested in transverse three-point bending at different strain rates and a span-to-depth ratio of 32. The composites were also tested under (constant load) creep conditions in bending.

CHARACTERIZATION OF MATRIX MATERIAL

In the case of matrix dominated failure modes the transverse strength of a composite is governed by the strength of the polymer matrix. In a composite the stress and strain fields in the matrix are complex. Consequently, in order to predict yielding of the matrix, expressions should be used which are able to describe yield under such complex stress situations. For the epoxy based composites studied in this research, a three-dimensional yield expression, usually referred to as pressure modified Eyring flow [11], is considered. This approach was initially proposed by Ward and Duckett [3,4] and expresses the stress state and deformation rate at the yield point in terms of the octahedral shear stress τ_{oct} and the octahedral shear rate $\dot{\gamma}_{oct}$, respectively:

$$\dot{\gamma}_{oct} = \dot{\gamma}_0(T) \sinh \left[\frac{\tau_{oct} v - P \Omega}{k T} \right] \quad (1)$$

where T is the absolute temperature, k is Boltzmann's constant, v is the shear activation volume, P is the hydrostatic pressure, Ω is the pressure activation volume and $\dot{\gamma}_0(T)$ is a temperature dependent parameter. In this study the temperature dependence can be neglected since only isothermal loading conditions are considered. For large stresses this relation can be reduced to:

$$\tau_{oct} = \tau_{0,oct} + \frac{k T}{v} \ln \dot{\gamma}_{oct} + \mu P \quad (2)$$

where $\tau_{0,oct}$ is a material constant and μ is the pressure dependence of the yield stress. Since, in general loading situations the hydrostatic pressure P will depend on the stress state at the yield point, it is convenient to express P as:

$$P = P_0 + \alpha \tau_{oct} \quad (3)$$

where α is a coefficient which is characteristic for each loading geometry (see Table 1) and P_0 is the environmental pressure. In our case, P_0 equals 0.1 MPa and can therefore be neglected. Introduction of Eq. 3 into Eq. 2 leads to:

$$\tau_{oct} = \frac{\tau_{0,oct} + \frac{k T}{v} \ln \dot{\gamma}_{oct}}{(1 - \mu \alpha)} \quad (4)$$

Table 1. The geometry factor α for each loading condition.

	α
Uniaxial extension	$-\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2}$
Uniaxial compression	$\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2}$
Planar extension	$-\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{6}$
Planar compression	$\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{6}$
Simple shear	0

The results of the uniaxial extension, planar extension, uniaxial compression, planar compression and simple shear test are presented in Fig. 1, where the octahedral shear stress is plotted versus the octahedral shear rate for all loading geometries. All experiments were performed at room temperature (295 Kelvin). The drawn lines are predicted by Eq. 4, using: $\tau_{0,oct} = 56.6$ MPa, $\mu = 0.126$ and $v = 3.5$ nm³, showing clearly that all experiments are in good agreement with this modified Eyring equation.

Figure 1. The octahedral shear stress versus octahedral strain rate for the various tests. The results are fitted with the pressure modified Eyring equation (Eq. 4).

MICROMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

To account for the complex stress and strain situation in a composite, micromechanical simulations are performed with the Finite Element Method (FEM). The mechanical behaviour of the matrix system is modelled with the compressible Leonov model which has shown its applicability for the description of the mechanical behaviour of polymers [9,10]. This model uses the same three-dimensional yield expression as presented in the previous Section.

Constitutive model

The characteristic material behaviour of polymers is presented in Fig. 2a by the solid line. This behaviour exhibits an initial elastic deformation (I), which becomes fully plastic (II) with increasing strain. At large deformations, an increasing strain hardening effect results in a rise in stress (III), which finally leads to fracture. The mechanical analogy, shown in Fig. 2b, was proposed by Haward and Thackray [12] and consists of a Maxwell model with a linear spring and an Eyring dashpot to account for the strain rate dependence of the yield point. The strain hardening behaviour has been modelled by a Gaussian, rubber elastic, spring placed in parallel. To facilitate finite element analysis a three-dimensional constitutive model is required. In this study the compressible Leonov model was used, which is described in detail elsewhere [9]. In this model the matrix material is regarded as a linear elastic, compressible solid up to the yield point, with a modulus of 3200 MPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.37. The yield behaviour of the material is described as a generalized Newtonian fluid with a flow characteristic according to the data presented in Fig. 1. The strain hardening behaviour was also modelled as a Gaussian, rubber elastic spring. The rubber shear modulus was estimated at 15 MPa, as determined experimentally with dynamic mechanical thermal analysis.

Figure 2. (a) Illustration of the characteristic behaviour of glassy polymer (solid line) with the fit of the compressible Leonov model (dashed line). True strain versus true stress is plotted. (b) Schematic representation of the compressible Leonov model.

Finite element model

In this study the calculations are based on a hexagonal fibre array, from which the repeating unit is shown in Fig. 3a. Due to symmetry only a quarter of this repeating unit needs to be modelled. The finite element mesh, representing a fibre volume fraction of 50% is shown in Fig. 3b. For the fibre 205 and for the epoxy matrix 675 generalized plane strain quadrilateral elements were used. Both mesh size and time increment were optimized by mesh refinement and time increment reduction.

Figure 3. (a) Representation of the hexagonal stacking. (b) The used mesh. Due to symmetry only a quarter of the repeating unit has to be modelled.

Failure criterion

Since there is no limit to the deformation in the constitutive model an additional failure criterion is needed. In this study a limiting value of 15% for the octahedral shear strain was chosen. This value was estimated from a numerical simulation of a tensile experiment at a global strain rate of 10^{-4} s^{-1} by evaluating the local strain state in the composite at an externally applied stress equal to the experimentally observed tensile strength. For the prediction of failure at other strain rates or under the influence of a statically applied stress (creep), a micromechanical simulation of the desired test was performed up to a global state of deformation where the local maximum of the octahedral shear strain equals the critical value of 15%.

MODEL VALIDATION

In this Section the results of the experiments on the unidirectional composites will be compared with the results of the numerical simulations. The experiments on the fibre-reinforced composites consisted of rate dependent strength measurements and creep experiments, both in three-point bending.

Rate dependent transverse strength

The unidirectional composites were transversely tested in three-point bending at constant strain rate. All tests were performed at ambient temperature and showed perfect linear elastic behaviour up to failure. The results of maximum stress versus strain rate of the composites in three-point bending are presented in Fig. 4. The error bars are the standard deviation of the experimental outcome. The predicted strain rate dependence of the transverse strength is represented by the solid line and shows that the experimental results are well described by a strain criterion, whereas a stress criterion gives erroneous results.

Figure 4. The strain rate versus the transverse strength. The results of three-point bending on transversely loaded composites (markers) are compared with numerical simulations (solid line) using the octahedral shear strain as a failure criterion.

From these results it can be concluded that the octahedral shear strain criterion gives promising results for the description of failure of transversely loaded composites.

Creep lifetime

Similar to the constant strain rate tests, the numerical predictions for creep failure were compared with experimental results. Again the local octahedral shear strain of the reference simulation (at a strain rate of 10^{-4} s^{-1}) is used to predict the creep time to failure for the different applied engineering stresses. The results of the experiments and the numerical simulations are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. The applied engineering stress versus time to break, showing the results of creep in three-point bending on transversely loaded unidirectional composites (markers) in comparison with the model prediction (solid line).

Figure 6. Contour plots of the evolution of the octahedral shear strain during creep at an engineering stress of 75 MPa. a-d, represent the various creep times (0-4100 s).

In all creep experiments the time needed to apply the constant engineering stress was negligible in comparison with the obtained creep time to failure. The applied stress was varied from 50 to 85 MPa. The solid line represents the predicted time to failure versus the engineering stress, using the octahedral shear strain criterion. It can be seen that the micromechanical model in combination with this failure criterion is able to describe time to fracture of the transversely loaded E-glass/epoxy composites. In Fig. 6 the evolution of the octahedral shear strain is illustrated. The graph clearly shows that the local strain in the 'plastic' region increases with time, whereas the strain in the 'elastic' region remains almost constant.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study it is demonstrated that the modified Eyring equation can be satisfactorily used for the description of the yield behaviour of the epoxy system under multiaxial loading conditions. The various multiaxial experiments also showed that the epoxy system clearly exhibits a pressure dependent yield behaviour. By introducing these parameters into the compressible Leonov model, numerical (FEM) simulations of the mechanical behaviour of the epoxy system could be performed. Micromechanical simulations of rate dependent transverse strength of unidirectional composites, showed the validity of a failure criterion based on a maximum local strain. Moreover, this failure criterion could be used for the prediction of creep time to failure.

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